

Three-Phase HFL-DVR With Independent Control of Each Phases

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Abstract— A power-frequency transformer connects the electricity grid to traditional dynamic voltage restorers (DVRs). Voltage drop and power losses are caused by these cumbersome and expensive transformers. Based on transformer-isolated topologies, this research proposes a high-frequency-link dynamic voltage restorer (HFL-DVR). In a three-phase system, this design allows each phase to operate independently. Enjoying cheap costs, minimal losses, and tiny size, it is a great choice. It is also devoid of transients caused by merinrush currents. HFL-DVR and other small-signal ac equivalent circuits are based on an averaged modelling method. In order to investigate how variables like dc-link voltage, grid voltage, and load current affect the HFL-DVR output, transfer functions are acquired. An integrated PID controller is used to achieve desirable qualities including steady-state error, transient overshoot, and setup time. As a result, it is possible to mitigate the impact of disturbances on HFL-DVR output. A 220V/50Hz HFL-DVR configuration is used to acquire the experimental findings. The theoretical aspects of the proposed DVR have been validated for both symmetrical and asymmetrical voltage sagging scenarios by comparing the simulation and experimental findings.

Glossary Terms—Asymmetrical voltage sag, small-signal equivalent circuit, PID controller, high-frequency-link dynamic voltage restorer (HFL-DVR).

INTRODUCTION

Voltage fluctuations are a major source of loss in distribution power systems, which in turn causes poor power quality. References [1], [2]. Due to the considerable advancements in insulated gate bipolar transistors and the simultaneous reduction in the

cost and physical size of the converters in DVR designs, dynamic voltage regulator (DVR) systems have recently showed promise in delivering a cost-efficient solution for low voltage (LV) systems [3, 4]. Conversely, high prices have been associated with uninterruptible power supply, which are seen as a substitute for regulating and compensating the load voltage. [6, 7]. Bulky power frequency transformers link traditional DVRs to the power grid. There are a number of drawbacks to this connection, including its expensive cost, big size, relatively high losses, saturation, and starting current [8]-[10]. Beyond that, the

Particularly with nonlinear loads, the voltage drop and rise in load voltage harmonics are caused by the impedance of the transformer [9]. There has been talk about transformerless DVRs as a way to make LV systems' DVRs smaller and cheaper [8]. This method necessitates the use of charging circuitry for each phase, in addition to increasing the number of switches and requiring separate capacitors for each phase in a three-phase system. The old structures' cost-effectiveness and operational improvement are called into question by these difficulties. A solution has been suggested in the form of an additional application for DVR systems, which additionally accounts for load voltage harmonics [9]. In this way, we can determine the series transformer's effective us-age [9]. The fifth and seventh harmonics of the power should flow through the grid-connected transformer, but high-frequency harmonics should not, as this DVR system rejects them. The passband limiting of a grid-connected transformer used for high-frequency harmonics was not taken into account by this method. The losses in the grid-connected transformer are also increased by high-order harmonics. To improve the voltage level

without requiring a transformer, an H-bridge cascaded multilevel inverter has been used in [10]. The complexity of this architecture and the number of power switches are substantial. Accordingly, under this topology, both cost and reliability go up. The article suggests a multi-level cascaded-type DVR that can be connected to the grid without the need for a transformer [11]. When compared to the two-level DVR, the multi-level DVR may support a prolonged ageing time. Furthermore, the study delves into harmonics in relation to the quantity of voltage levels generated by the DVR system. Research has shown that a decrease in switching losses may be achieved by increasing the number of switches and the systems that govern and drive them. The needs of LV applications, which call for tiny, lightweight, and inexpensive systems, cannot be met by this method. One recent proposal for single-phase compensation makes use of an interphase ac-ac

topology [12]. Due to the lack of a storage device, this cost-effective architecture enjoys a diminutive size. But symmetrical voltage sags are not something it can fix. For a single-phase system, the idea of high-frequency-link DVR has been put forth [13], [14]. Significant benefits, such as a reduction in size and weight, are brought about by the introduction of transformer into the converter. As a result, expenses can go down. Computers and medical equipment are among the devices that this DVR is well-suited to safeguard [7]. To address voltage sag in a three-phase system with a peak voltage of around 175 V, more research into this method has been conducted in [15]. In order to prevent harsh switching, which is particularly common in cycloconverters, an appropriate control technique has been developed. Regrettably, the results of each stage cannot

Fig.1. Proposed HFL-DVR and thevenin circuits of utility grid as well as load.

on their own, since a single inverter provides power to each phase. However, this DVR can only compensate for three-phase voltage sags of the same magnitude. The article suggests a better design that makes use of a high-frequency-link dynamic voltage regulator (HFL-DVR). In contrast to [14] and [15], the structure not only offers independent operating conditions for each phase, but it also reduces the number of switches. Consequently, not only were the operating conditions improved, but size and weight reductions were also achieved. The suggested DVR eliminates the need for phase-specific energy storage devices, in contrast to transformerless DVR architectures [8, 10]. This results in decreased size, weight, and maintenance needs. It offers galvanic isolation and electrical safety while boosting voltage from an LV battery to an HFL transformer. Using a small-signal ac model, we examine the HFL-DVR's behaviour as it compensates the grid

voltage during voltage sagging. An analysis of the HFL-DVR's behaviour is conducted after obtaining the circuit's transfer functions and studying the influence of the PID controller and feedback loop. The HFL-DVR's transient response may therefore be sufficiently rapid and dampened with sufficient phase margin at all anticipated operating points. Furthermore, the impact of disturbances like grid voltage and load current on the HFL-DVR's output voltage is substantially mitigated. The theoretical components of the controller and the proposed DVR system are enhanced by comparisons between simulation results and actual observations. Chapter I: Enhancing Fluorescence-Based Molecular Biology The suggested DVR system's power circuit is shown in Figure 1. [13] and [14] presented the HFL cyclo converter that the circuit is built on. There are four primary components of the circuit. An initial component is a voltage source full bridge inverter (VSFBI) that includes a DC storage system (battery) and four switches (S1-S4).

TABLE I
COMPARATIVE STUDY OF HFL-DVR AND PRIOR DVRs

Definition	Proposed HFL-DVR		[14]	[15]
	Single phase	Three phase		
No. of semiconductor devices	8	20	12	28
No. of dc link storage elements	1	1	1	1
No. of HFIT	1	3	1	1
Cost efficient, regarding the design simplicity, the number of power switches, drive circuit, heat sinks and the HFITs	Better	Better	Good	Good
Power to the cost ratio	Good	The best	Good	Good
Size and weight, regarding the number of power switches, drive circuit, heat sinks and the number of HFITs	Better	Better	Good	Good
Power to the volume ratio	Good	The best	Good	Good
Power losses including switching losses, conducting losses and fixed losses	The Lowest	Low	Low	Low
Efficiency regarding the power losses	The best	Good	Good	Good
Reliability regarding independent operation capability of phases (ports)	The best	Good	Good	Good

Symbol	Definition	Value
V_g	Grid voltage at PCC	220V rms 50 Hz
L_x	Equivalent inductance at PCC	100 mH
L_L	Thévenin equivalent inductance of load	55 mH
R_L	Thévenin equivalent resistance of load	100Ω
V_d	de-link voltage	120V
$n=n_s/n_p$	HFIT turn ratio	1
r_{on}	Switch resistance	0.1Ω
L_f	Output filter inductance	5 mH
C_f	Output filter capacitance	20 μF
r_L	Resistance of L_f	0.2Ω
r_c	Resistance of C_f	2Ω
f_s	Switching frequency	12.5 kHz

The state error of the system indicates that a better control system should be designed in order to enhance the control signal ϕ . Consequently, the load current, $v_g(s)$, and $v_d(s)$ are all irrelevant to the regulated output voltage.

Dynamic Mode Load-DVR, Part II
 This part details the development of the system's dynamic model, which incorporates the HFL-DVR, power system (load and grid), and PID compensator. Also mentioned is the influence of the compensator on the zygote stem. Using a linear combination of the independent inputs, the output voltage variation v_{dvr} may be stated as follows:

The poles of the systems diverge much further from the theoretical one as q grows [see Fig.8(a)]. According to Figure 8(b), the incr

tenth of the crossover frequency, or 350 Hz. The PID controller's Bode diagram is seen in Figure 12. Part C: The Paid DVR System The influence of feedback and control over transfer functions are now being investigation. A comparison is made between the compensated and uncompensated systems. Figure 13 shows the Root Locus and the Bode diagram of the compensated open-loop gain $T(s)$ when the influence of compensators is taken into account. If the phase margin of the system is about 112.0 degrees and the magnitude of the $GC(s)$ is approximately 75 dB, then the amplitude of the closed-loop disturbance-to-output transfer function may be assumed to be zero at dc. $vdvr/vrefLoad$ is the unit step response of the compensated system that is shown in Image 14. The system has a setup time of less than 2 ms, and the overshoot is less than 5%. The system's reaction to changes in the small-signal control signal ϕ has presumably been enhanced, if Fig. 14 is compared to Fig. 9. Zero has also been achieved in the steady-state error of system responsiveness. As demonstrated in Figure 15, the input voltage's step response to the output voltage is $vdvr/vdis$. The output voltage may increase to 15 V without a compensator and reaches 2 V in the steady state in 0.016 s. After 0.018 seconds, the output voltage reaches 0.0037 V in the steady state, after an overshoot of about 1 V caused by the compensator effect.

The square of the input voltage to the output voltage, denoted as $vdvr/vg$, is shown in Image 16. As seen in

Fig.12. Bode diagram of a PID controller.

$$26 \text{ fp} = 1.9844 = 5.95 \text{ dB}$$

Including an inverted zero significantly enhances the low-frequency control. To improve the low-frequency control of the output voltage, we may raise the loop gain at frequencies below 350 Hz by selecting the inverted zero frequency equal to one-

Figure 17. The operation of the DVR when subjected to a balanced three-phase voltage drop.(a) The outcomes of the simulation and (b) the observations (10 ms/div). electrical current. While voltage sag has no effect on load, the load voltage stays the same. Here, with the imbalanced voltage sag, the findings from the experiments are in good agreement with the results from the simulations. The ability of the proposed HFL- DVR to correct for imbalanced voltage sags is well shown.

Dynamics of HFL-DVR (C) Here we report on our investigation into the effects of grid voltage V_g , load impedance, and dc-link voltage V on the HFL-DVR's operating conditions. V_{gis} , the source voltage, is subject to an imbalanced sag voltage state from t_1 to t_5 , which is nonsinusoidal. Moreover, from time t_2 to time t_4 , the load resistance rises from 100 to 2000 ohms, and

from time t_3 to time t_5 , the dc-link voltage V_d falls from 120 to 90 ohms. This allows for the independent and standalone examination of the effects of V_g , load, and V_d . In agreement-

Fig. 18. DVR performance under unbalanced three-phase voltage sag.(a)Simulationand(b)measurements results(10ms/div).

CONCLUSION

An enhanced DVR system architecture is suggested in this research; it is directly linked to the grid via the HFIT. As the number of semiconductor devices is reduced and only one storage element is needed

for all phases, the proposed HFL-DVR has comparatively low loss, compact size, and light weight. The transfer function of the system may be obtained using a small-signal ac model. The effect of input variation on DVR output is examined by use of transfer functions. It has been shown that the PID controller may inhibit

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